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From support measures to inclusive education participation and progression: the development of support courses in Swiss vocational education and training

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ABSTRACT

Support courses have been a cornerstone of Swiss vocational education and training since 1978. This article analyses their historical development and their significance for inclusive vocational education and training, educational equity and participation, and progression (SDG 4). Based on a historical-analytical document analysis of 44 laws, education policy texts, evaluation reports and scientific literature (1978–2025), target groups, functions, legal frameworks, didactics, governance and effects were analysed using deductive and inductive approaches. The analysis identifies three phases, namely introduction and establishment (1978–2003), legal realignment (2004–2019) and pandemic-related responses together with future-oriented developments (from 2020 onwards). Over time, there has been a paradigm shift from deficit-oriented tutoring to resource-oriented, inclusive support, with an expanded focus on interdisciplinary skills, language learning and psychosocial dimensions. Support courses are now a core element of inclusive vocational education and training and contribute significantly to equal opportunities, educational participation and progression. Although international transfer is possible, it requires adaptation to administrative structures, teacher training and cultural contexts. This Swiss case study offers insights for international debates on educational equity, inclusion and educational participation, as well as progression. Future research should evaluate effectiveness, promote destigmatisation and develop sustainable administrative models.

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Introduction

Around the world, vocational education and training systems face the challenge of ensuring educational equity and participation for different groups of learners, as stipulated in Article 24 of the UN CRPD (Schweizerische Eidgenossenschaft, 2006). International agendas such as SDG 4 ‘Quality Education’ and UNESCO programmes on lifelong education emphasise support measures as central to successful educational pathways (OECD, 2021; UNESCO, 2016). This article

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focuses on institutionally organised support services in formal and non-formal settings within vocational education and training. Studies show that support instruments reduce school dropouts and facilitate transitions into employment (Cedefop, 2016; Cerda-Navarro et al., 2017). An OECD case study also points out that coordinated support services can reduce dropouts (OECD, 2025). This is particularly true for dual systems, as accompanying measures can stabilise at-risk apprentices and reduce dropouts (Deissingner, 2015; Kammermann et al., 2011; Scharnhorst & Kammermann, 2017). In Switzerland, around two-thirds of young people start basic vocational training (SBFI, 2022). At the same time, around a quarter experience a premature termination of their apprenticeship contract during their initial vocational training (BFS, 2023). In addition to academic performance, family, school and workplace factors, language barriers and insufficiently coordinated support services also have an impact on training success (Häfeli & Schellenberg, 2009; Stutz et al., 2016; Todisco et al., 2020). Against this backdrop, support courses have played a central role since 1978 (Schweizerische Eidgenossenschaft, 1978). They were originally designed as a compensatory measure for 'lower-performing apprentices'. With the reform of the Vocational Training Act in 2004, the objectives were expanded (Schweizerische Eidgenossenschaft, 2002). Today, support courses work in collaboration with training companies to help apprentices successfully complete vocational school. This represents a shift from deficit-oriented tutoring to resource-oriented, individualised support. They are considered a cornerstone of inclusive vocational education and training and contribute to educational equity, participation and progression (Grassi et al., 2014; Scharnhorst & Kammermann, 2018; Wüthrich, 2023).

Although support courses are enshrined in law and education policy, there has been no comprehensive analysis of their development to date. Existing studies highlight specific aspects. These include implementation, target groups and effects (Grassi et al., 2014; Grossenbacher, 1993; Hasler, 2016; Kammermann & Heller, 2019; Schneider, 2014; Wettstein & Broch, 1979). However, they do not provide a systematic historical overview. As Switzerland, with its dual system, is often regarded as a reference model internationally, such an analysis is also relevant for international debates (Euler, 2019; Hoffman & Schwartz, 2015). This article therefore examines the following questions.

- (1)) How have support courses in Swiss vocational education and training developed institutionally, pedagogically and functionally since 1978?
- (2)) What role do support courses play in promoting educational equity, inclusive vocational education and training, educational participation and progression, and what impact does this have on effectiveness, governance and international transferability?

The article contributes to Swiss vocational education and training research and provides impetus for international discussions on support instruments in the context of equal opportunities, inclusion, educational participation and progression.

Support courses in the context of inclusive vocational education and training

The Swiss vocational education and training (VET) system follows a dual structure with three learning locations: the workplace, vocational school and inter-company courses (SBFI, 2022). Practical training takes place in companies, theoretical content is taught at vocational school, and inter-company courses combine both (Wettstein et al., 2014). In this article, the term ‘support courses’ refers to legally established, school-organised additional courses designed to ensure successful completion of vocational school and thus successful completion of basic vocational training (BBG, Art. 22 para. 4; Schweizerische Eidgenossenschaft, 2002). In the official English translation of Swiss VET law, Stützkurse are referred to as remedial courses. In this article, however, the term support courses is used as a broader analytical label because it better captures the current function of these provisions in Swiss VET: they are no longer framed merely as compensatory remedial measures, but increasingly as inclusive and resource-oriented forms of support linked to participation, educational success and progression. They are arranged as needed by agreement between the vocational school, the company and the apprentice; in the event of disagreement, the canton decides (BBG, Art. 22 para. 4). In this article, the term ‘apprentices’ refers to learners in Swiss dual initial vocational education and training (IVET), that is individuals undertaking company-based training while attending a vocational school.

The legal basis for basic vocational education and training is the Vocational Education and Training Act (BBG) of 2004 (Schweizerische Eidgenossenschaft, 2002), supplemented by the Vocational Education and Training Ordinance (BBV) (Schweizerische Eidgenossenschaft, 2003). The two-year basic vocational training programme is aimed at IVET learners (apprentices) who are primarily practice-oriented and meet lower academic requirements. It concludes with the Federal Vocational Certificate (EBA). In addition, apprentices receive support in the form of individual technical guidance (fiB), in which a trained specialist supports apprentices whose training success is at risk (SBFI, 2014). Responsibility for implementing fiB lies with the individual cantons (Stern & von Dach, 2018). Around 30% of graduates of a two-year basic vocational training programme go on to complete a three- or four-year basic vocational training programme, which leads to the Federal Certificate of Competence (EFZ) (BFS, 2023). A characteristic feature of the Swiss system is its high degree of permeability, which allows access to further education at every stage and supports educational participation and progression (BFS, 2023). In this article, this frame of reference is limited to institutionally organised formal and non-formal support services within Swiss vocational education and training. Informal learning outside the remit of the education authorities is not covered by this study.

At the same time, the education system in Switzerland is highly stratified and characterised by early selection, which can exacerbate educational disadvantages and underlines the need for individual support (Powell & Hadjar, 2018). Although vocational education and training ensures a high level of employability, cantonal differences remain (Gonon & Bonoli, 2025; SBFI, 2022). The 26 Swiss cantons, comparable to states or provinces, enjoy extensive autonomy in education policy. Switzerland also has four language regions, with vocational education and training programmes offered in three

regions. The proportion of people completing basic vocational education and training is higher in German-speaking Switzerland than in the French- and Italian-speaking regions (BFS, 2023), which also highlights the challenges of comprehensive inclusion and cultural differences (Gonon, 2013).

Support courses have been enshrined in Swiss VET legislation since 1978 and were originally introduced for lower-performing VET learners (Schweizerische Eidgenossenschaft, 1978). With the reform of the VET Act (BBG) in 2004, the target group was expanded and support courses became accessible to all VET learners (Schweizerische Eidgenossenschaft, 2002, 2003). The legal basis is provided by the BBG (Art. 21–22) and the BBV (Art. 20). Support courses are part of the curriculum. The BBV specifies in particular that support courses must be planned in such a way that they do not significantly impair training and that they must not exceed an average of half a day per week during working hours (Schweizerische Eidgenossenschaft, 2003).

This article focuses on support courses. The theoretical framework can be described in three dimensions: (1) compensatory support as a contribution to educational equity, (2) control as an instrument for ensuring training success, and (3) inclusion as a human rights principle. These three dimensions also formed the main deductive categories of the document analysis (see Method). Against the backdrop of increasing social diversity (Wüthrich, 2024), greater psychological stress among apprentices (Schmocker et al., 2025) and limited integrative resources at secondary level II, support courses are gaining importance as an inclusive educational tool. With the ratification of the UN CRPD in 2014, Switzerland is obliged to ensure inclusive vocational education and training (Scharnhorst & Kammermann, 2018). Inclusion is understood not only as an educational concept, but also as a human rights principle (Katzenbach, 2017).

Switzerland pursues a broad understanding of inclusion, as defined in the UN CRPD (Bach, 2018). According to Rützel (2014), this understanding takes into account various dimensions of heterogeneity and attempts to meet individual needs. From this perspective, all people should be enabled to develop and realise their personal potential (Rützel, 2013), an approach that is also supported by UNESCO (Bach, 2018). A broad understanding of inclusion thus underlines the need for targeted educational support measures. At the same time, support courses can be placed within the context of SDG 4 and UNESCO programmes on education throughout life, with the focus on participation and progression in institutionally organised educational pathways (UNESCO, 2016). This does not imply any statement about informal learning outside institutional responsibilities. Support courses can therefore be interpreted as part of a more comprehensive support system that enables equal opportunities and individualised learning, even if they are not explicitly defined as inclusion measures in law. The literature also points to the importance of accompanying measures to promote inclusion in vocational education and training (Duc & Kammermann, 2024; Häfeli & Schellenberg, 2009). This creates an area of tension, as basic vocational education, unlike compulsory schooling, has only limited integrative resources; special education specialists are not usually systematically provided for in vocational school classes (Wüthrich, 2024).

The international relevance of support courses stems from Switzerland's role as a reference model for dual systems (Hoffman & Schwartz, 2015). While comparable support measures in Germany or Austria are often project-based and temporary, Swiss support courses are systematic and long-term (Miesera et al., 2022). As an exemplary contrast, recent policy and regulatory documents for England show that additional learning support in the 16–19 age

group is framed, among other things, by tutoring formats and requirements or retraining in English and mathematics (Department for Education, 2024; Office of Qualifications and Examinations Regulation (Ofqual), 2024). Wolf (2011) offers an earlier educational policy classification on this subject. Overall, international comparisons indicate that curricular embedding, governance and institutional standardisation of support services vary between countries (Kammermann et al., 2011). These differences show that Swiss support courses are an interesting example for countries that want to introduce dual vocational education and training or make existing systems more inclusive. International transfer strategies should be understood as context-sensitive adaptations, because dual vocational education and training cannot be exported on a one-to-one basis and its transfer depends on institutional, cultural and economic conditions as well as on the respective demand side (Euler, 2019). Transfer can also be described as a process of translation and negotiation between the actors involved, in which positions are coordinated and adapted to contextual conditions (Maurer, 2025). In summary, the theoretical dimensions and international comparisons show that support courses are an innovative example of how compensatory support, governance and inclusion can be combined.

Method

The study is based on a historical-analytical research design (Bowen, 2009), which is established in historical education research and has proven itself for the reconstruction of long-term developments (Oelkers, 2001; Tenorth, 2010). The aim was to trace the development of support courses in Swiss vocational education and training over almost five decades, identify turning points and analyse their significance for inclusive vocational education and training, as well as for educational participation and progression in institutionally organised educational pathways. Document analysis was chosen as the methodological approach because it provides access to normative, educational policy and scientific discourses that are central to the reconstruction of institutional developments (Döring & Bortz, 2016). The study uses existing documents as its data basis (Medjedović, 2014). Other methods, such as interviews, were considered less suitable for the historical research question, as they are more strongly influenced by retrospective distortions (e.g. memory effects, selective perception or social desirability).

The analysis is based on a corpus of 44 documents selected in a multi-stage process from a total of 132 identified sources. The starting point was a systematic search of official legal databases, cantonal law collections, specialist portals and scientific databases. Documents were included if they explicitly mentioned the term ‘support course’ or functionally equivalent terms, referred to basic vocational education and training, and covered the period from 1978 to 2025. The main reasons for exclusion were lack of relevance to vocational education and training or lack of substantial content on support courses. To increase transparency, the composition of the corpus is shown by document type in Table 1.

Table 1. Composition of the document corpus ($N = 44$).

Document type	Examples	n
National regulations	BBG, BBV	2
Cantonal regulations	Ordinances, directives	8
Evaluation/implementation	Evaluation reports	8
Scientific literature	Articles, monographs	17
Other	Programmes, reports	9
Total		44

The document types were coded using the same category system, but were not weighted equally. Primary sources formed the normative frame of reference. Secondary sources were used for contextualisation and triangulation. Scientific literature was used for theoretical classification and plausibility checks. Due to Switzerland's federal organisation, statements on the national framework are primarily based on federal law and national documents. Cantonal sources were also included to illustrate implementation variants. The study does not claim to be a complete survey of all cantons.

The evaluation was carried out using MAXQDA 24 (VERBI Software [VERBI], 2025) and followed the principles of qualitative content analysis (Kuckartz & Rädiker, 2024; Mayring, 2022). The category system was derived deductively from the three theoretical dimensions of compensation promotion, governance and inclusion, and supplemented by inductive categories. The deductive categories covered dimensions 1 to 8, while categories 9 and 10 and several subcategories were developed inductively (see Table 2).

Examples illustrate the coding process. For category 1 (target groups), one excerpt reads: *'The school ensures that learners with academic deficits in individual subjects receive support over a certain period of time'* (Luzern, 2006). For category 4.3 (teacher qualification in support courses), an early description states: *'Where possible, they are led by experienced main teachers and begin with a few lessons on learning techniques'* (Wettstein & Broch, 1979). Such examples were documented in memos. The division of developments into three phases was based on clear breaks in legislation and political discourse. The first phase (1978–2003) begins with the legal anchoring of support courses in the Vocational Training Act (Schweizerische Eidgenossenschaft, 1978) and ends with the 2004 reform. The second phase (2004–2019) is marked by the entry into force of the new Vocational Training Act (Schweizerische Eidgenossenschaft, 2002). The third phase (from 2020 onwards) encompasses responses to the coronavirus pandemic and the increasing individualisation and inclusion of basic vocational education and training (Schellenberg et al., 2021; Wüthrich, 2023). The results are reported chronologically along these three phases. AI-supported suggestions in MAXQDA were used to assist with coding. The final coding and interpretation were carried out by the author (Kuckartz & Rädiker, 2024).

Several strategies were used for quality assurance. Validity was increased by triangulating different types of documents, transparency was ensured by documenting all steps

Table 2. Category system for document analysis.

Main category	Subcategory
1. Target groups	
2. Functions	2.1 Special educational measures 2.2 Determination of support needs
3. Legal framework	
4. Didactic orientation	4.1 Specific teaching materials 4.2 Design 4.3 Teacher qualifications in support courses 4.4 Conditions of participation
5. Political reasons	
6. Administration and financing	6.1 Cooperation and networking
7. Impact/results	
8. Social context	
9. Perception and acceptance of support courses	
10. Supplementary services	

of the analysis, and reflexivity was promoted by critically reflecting on the role of the researcher in order to minimise possible bias. As only publicly available documents were analysed, no formal ethical approval was required.

Results

The results are presented chronologically along the three identified phases (1978–2003, 2004–2019, and from 2020 onwards). While the category system formed the analytical framework, the results within each phase are structured to highlight historical developments.

Introduction and establishment of support courses (1978–2003)

The introduction of support courses in 1978 marked the beginning of a systematically promoted support structure in Swiss vocational education and training (VET). With their legal anchoring in the Federal Vocational Education and Training Act (Schweizerische Eidgenossenschaft, 1978), they were established as one of three support measures for ‘weaker young people’, alongside pre-apprenticeships and supported apprenticeships (Riedo, 2000; Wettstein & Broch, 1979). Cantonal regulations governed implementation at regional level (Solothurn, 1977; Zürich, 1987). Provision was needs-based and subject to approval, which indicates that control was initially only partially systematised. Originally, the courses were aimed at apprentices with insufficient prior education or poor academic performance (Solothurn, 1977). However, it soon became apparent that the problems went beyond subject-specific deficits and were often linked to learning and working techniques as well as psychosocial stress (Grossenbacher, 1993; SIBP, 2002). Accordingly, the support courses evolved from compensatory tutoring to a diagnostic and support process that strengthened learning and problem-solving skills as well as personal development (Grossenbacher, 1993; SIBP, 2002). The assessment of needs was systematised and carried out by teachers, school reports and referrals from companies and vocational schools (SIBP, 2002).

The didactic design of the courses also evolved. Early approaches emphasised individual support, basic learning strategies and a supportive learning environment (Grossenbacher, 1993; Solothurn, 1977). The literature describes a problem of motivation and stigmatisation in compulsory forms and emphasises a stronger focus on voluntary participation (SIBP, 2002). Time-limited modules and learning journals were used to promote self-reflection (Büchel, 1991; Grossenbacher, 1993). Small groups were considered a key framework condition (typically around 6–10 apprentices) (SIBP, 2002; Wettstein & Broch, 1979). The professionalisation of teachers progressed. Qualified specialists with additional pedagogical and psychological knowledge were recommended; corresponding further training courses were expanded (Büchel, 1991; Grossenbacher, 1993; Wettstein & Broch, 1979). Cooperation and networking were increasingly recognised as crucial. Success factors included cooperation between support teachers and class teachers, the involvement of training companies and parents, and coordination with cantonal authorities (Grossenbacher, 1993; SIBP, 2002; Solothurn, 1977).

Document analyses report positive effects such as improved semester grades, increased self-confidence and better chances of successful completion (SIBP, 2002). At

the same time, there were challenges. In case reports, the benefits of individual course formats are sometimes perceived as low, especially when integration and support are inadequate (Stieger, 2003). At the same time, individual documents show reluctance or even rejection of such offerings (Grossenbacher, 1993; Wettstein & Broch, 1979). Although the courses were free of charge for participants, they required forward-looking financial planning and sustainable budgeting at cantonal level (SIBP, 2002; Solothurn, 1977; Zürich, 1978). In summary, the period from 1978 to 2003 can be described as a pioneering conceptual phase. Support courses developed from compensatory measures into a pedagogically sound instrument, characterised by individualisation, metacognitive elements, professionalisation of teachers and increasing cooperation between stakeholders to ensure educational success.

Legal realignment (2004–2019)

Between 2004 and 2019, support courses in Swiss vocational education and training were legally consolidated and institutionally anchored. With the introduction of the revised VET Act (BBG) and the VET Ordinance (BBV), vocational schools were required to offer targeted support courses, particularly when the educational success of VET learners was at risk (Schweizerische Eidgenossenschaft, 2002, 2003). This created a formally guaranteed right to support courses, which could comprise up to half a day per week and could be attended without loss of pay. Cantonal regulations and implementation documents specified the implementation, scope and financing in detail and highlighted differences in cantonal control (Bern, 2006; Luzern, 2006).

The target groups during this period were diverse. The support courses were primarily aimed at VET learners with academic deficits, learning difficulties or insufficient basic knowledge in core subjects such as mathematics and language (Minder, 2011; Scharnhorst & Kammermann, 2017). At the same time, the documents emphasise a broad heterogeneity that also includes social and linguistic disadvantages (Grassi et al., 2014; Scharnhorst & Kammermann, 2017). Individual subject-specific counselling (fiB) gained particular importance in the two-year basic vocational training programme and placed support courses more firmly within a network of complementary support services (Kammermann et al., 2015; SBFI, 2014). The growing need for language support, especially for young people who immigrated late, is repeatedly described as a key development (Schneider, 2014; Stutz et al., 2016).

The didactic design of the support courses was characterised by individualisation, flexibility and time-limited, needs-oriented planning (Puipe, 2006; Stern & von Dach, 2018). Various formats such as learning workshops, coaching elements or team teaching are reported as implementation variants, partly with the aim of supporting transitions to three- and four-year programmes (Scharnhorst & Kammermann, 2017; Stern & von Dach, 2018). The courses pursued process-oriented and performance-related goals and focused on self-organisation, learning strategies and subject-specific skills (Grassi et al., 2014; Häfeli et al., 2012; Scharnhorst & Kammermann, 2017). Early detection and continuous support are repeatedly presented as conducive conditions (Grassi et al., 2014).

Despite institutional anchoring, challenges remained. Documents report evidence of stigmatisation, acceptance problems and misjudgements that can affect willingness to

participate (Minder, 2011; Puipe, 2006). Cooperation with training companies remained difficult. Not all employers were willing to release apprentices for support courses or recognise their relevance (Minder, 2011; Stutz et al., 2016). The qualification of teachers also remained an issue. Further training in diagnostics, individual support and communication is described as necessary (Grassi et al., 2014; Kammermann et al., 2015; Minder, 2011). Financing and resources were a recurring source of tension. While some documents assume sufficient funds, others refer to scarce or precarious resources, especially in language support (German as a second language) (Kammermann & Heller, 2019; Minder, 2011; Stern & von Dach, 2018; Stutz et al., 2016).

Although support courses were enshrined in law, empirical data show that they were not fully utilised. Only around 20% of apprentices whose training contracts were terminated actually took part in such courses (Hasler, 2016). Several cantonal framework concepts aimed to combine counselling, technical support and guidance in a more coherent manner, addressing inclusion, educational participation and progression within the framework of institutionally organised educational pathways (Kammermann & Heller, 2019; Schneider, 2014). Nevertheless, systematic evaluation remained limited. There have been reports of positive effects in terms of school performance and training qualifications, but at the same time a lack of clear scientific evidence has been highlighted (Kammermann & Heller, 2019; Minder, 2011).

In summary, the period from 2004 to 2019 reflects the transformation of support courses from selective interventions to a regular component of vocational education and training. They gained particular importance in the two-year basic education programme through their integration into fiB. Legal consolidation and institutional anchoring went hand in hand with a differentiation of offerings, although persistence in terms of acceptance, resources, qualification issues and evaluation remain visible.

Responses to the pandemic and shaping the future (since 2020)

The COVID-19 pandemic led to the temporary closure of vocational schools in Switzerland in spring 2020. Teaching was reorganised under online and hybrid conditions, which also forced support courses to adopt new formats at short notice. A key issue during this period was apprentices' perceptions and acceptance of support courses. The findings reveal a tension between perceived benefits and risks of stigmatisation (Mathis, 2024; Schellenberg et al., 2021). Participation could be associated with stigma, which had a negative impact on social status and motivation (Mathis, 2024). Some apprentices rated support courses and learning coaching as only moderately helpful (Schellenberg et al., 2021). This brings the institutional embedding and communicative framing of the programmes to the fore as influencing factors for acceptance and use, alongside their subject-specific orientation (Mathis, 2024; Schellenberg et al., 2021).

In terms of function and didactic orientation, support courses continued to address academic deficits. Language-related support programmes, especially in German, are described as relevant for learning opportunities (Wüthrich, 2023). At the same time, there has been an increase in individualised and needs-oriented formats that are more strongly geared towards specific learning requirements (Wüthrich, 2023). This is discussed in particular in the context of heterogeneous learning groups and migration biographies. With individualisation comes an increased need for diagnostics and tailor-

made concept development (Wüthrich, 2023). At the organisational level, vocational schools were given more leeway to design support courses flexibly (Wüthrich, 2023). Documents report a variety of implementation models, including team teaching, additional resources and adaptive course formats. However, increased autonomy is accompanied by tensions regarding comparability and quality assurance. Differences in resources, limited coordination and limited resources are repeatedly cited as obstacles to sustainable implementation (Todisco et al., 2020).

Another development concerns the increasing integration of support courses into more comprehensive inclusive support concepts. They are often no longer used as isolated measures, but in combination with other forms of support (Schellenberg et al., 2021). This broadens the focus beyond subject-specific deficits to include interdisciplinary and psychosocial aspects (Schmocker et al., 2022). In summary, the period after 2020 can be described as a phase in which support courses have become more flexible and more closely integrated into comprehensive support structures. Persistent areas of tension relate to acceptance, resources and ensuring uniform quality standards (Schellenberg et al., 2021; Todisco et al., 2020).

Discussion

This article has traced the historical development of support courses in Swiss vocational education and training since 1978 and shown how an originally deficit-oriented instrument gradually developed into a more resource-oriented and inclusive support approach. The three phases identified, namely introduction and establishment, legal reorientation, and pandemic-related responses with a focus on the future, mark key turning points as well as structural continuities. Over time, institutional frameworks and didactic concepts have changed, while demands have increased due to digitalisation, growing heterogeneity among apprentices and the need for continuous learning. The findings can be classified into the three analytical dimensions outlined in the theoretical framework: compensatory support to reduce educational disadvantage, control through legal anchoring and steering, and inclusion as a human rights principle and educational policy goal. Taken together, they show that support courses are no longer merely a supplementary remedial measure, but have increasingly become part of a broader support structure within vocational education and training.

The first research question on the institutional, didactic and functional development of support courses can be answered clearly. The starting point was a response to acute learning deficits. However, support courses have developed into an integral part of vocational education and training. Today, they go beyond technical support and operationalise principles of inclusive education (Katzenbach, 2017). Their legal anchoring in the BBG and BBV, together with the gradual professionalisation of teachers, also shows that support courses act as a governance mechanism to stabilise training success. At the same time, this development should not be interpreted as a simple success story. Support courses have broadened from subject-specific remediation towards metacognitive, linguistic and psychosocial forms of support. This shift is consistent with literature that conceptualises inclusion not only as access to existing structures, but as the adaptation of educational arrangements to learner heterogeneity (Katzenbach, 2017; Rützel, 2014). Yet the findings also show that support courses remain embedded in a highly stratified

system characterised by early selection and cantonal variation. Their growing relevance therefore points both to stronger inclusion-oriented support and to the persistence of structural inequalities that continue to require compensatory measures.

The second research question concerned the role of support courses in educational equity, inclusion, educational participation and progression. The findings indicate that support courses promote training success and strengthen interdisciplinary skills. They thus contribute to SDG 4 and to inclusion-oriented objectives in vocational education and training. More specifically, support courses can be understood as a bridge between formal access to VET and actual opportunities to succeed within it. Equal access does not automatically translate into equal chances of completion, progression or transition into employment. In this respect, support courses help learners remain in training, cope with institutional demands and continue along their educational pathways. This links the findings to broader debates on lifelong education, in which participation includes not only entry into education but also sustained progression within institutionally organised pathways. From an international perspective, the systematic integration of support courses into Swiss vocational education and training is remarkable. The Swiss model can therefore be classified as a comparatively strong institutional and legally anchored support instrument, although this article offers only an exemplary contextualisation rather than a systematic country comparison. In terms of gradual institutional change, support courses can be understood as the result of an expansion of governance characterised by legal consolidation and path dependency (Maurer, 2022; Streeck & Thelen, 2005). This suggests that inclusive change in VET may emerge incrementally through the reinterpretation and expansion of existing policy instruments, rather than only through comprehensive reform.

The results also identify several implications for policy and practice. First, the professionalisation of teachers through further training in inclusive education should be strengthened in order to identify learning needs more precisely and improve effectiveness. Second, destigmatisation is crucial so that support courses are perceived as a regular part of education rather than as an exception. This is directly relevant to participation: if support courses are socially framed as a sign of failure, willingness to participate may remain limited even where legal entitlement exists. Third, there is a need for systemic anchoring that addresses not only technical knowledge but also social, emotional and metacognitive skills. This includes curricular integration, continuous evaluation and long-term funding, complemented by binding coordination and forward-looking resource planning. The findings also underline the importance of learning-site cooperation. In dual VET systems, support cannot be organised by vocational schools alone, because participation partly depends on the willingness of training companies to release apprentices and recognise the value of support measures.

Empirical evidence from cantonal practice shows clear differences. In some cases, support courses are widespread and well funded; in others, they are limited or costly. Unclear guidelines, inconsistent responsibilities and scarce resources make coherent implementation difficult. Policy implementation literature helps explain why a common legal framework gives rise to uneven cantonal practices (Hill & Hupe, 2021; Lipsky, 1980). Support courses are implemented by local actors whose decisions are shaped by discretionary room for manoeuvre, but also constrained by resources, organisational structures and institutional routines. From this

perspective, cantonal differences in scope, funding, accessibility and acceptance can be understood as implementation effects rather than as simple deviations from an otherwise coherent model. This helps explain why legal consolidation and uneven implementation can coexist within a federalised governance structure such as Switzerland's.

In an international comparison, the Swiss model is an example of adaptive vocational education and training that permanently anchors support services in institutions. The development of support courses shows how inclusive objectives can be implemented in institutionally organised educational pathways. At the same time, the Swiss case should not be interpreted as a model for direct transfer. Rather, it provides an analytically useful example of how support measures can become legally anchored, institutionally stabilised and progressively reinterpreted in more inclusive and resource-oriented terms. Future research should therefore examine the effectiveness of support courses more systematically, including the effects of targeted teacher training and governance arrangements. Comparative studies across cantons would be particularly valuable in clarifying how different governance arrangements, resource constellations and forms of cooperation shape implementation and outcomes. In addition, qualitative studies involving apprentices, teachers, in-company trainers and cantonal actors would help capture perspectives that remain absent from document-based analysis.

Limitations

This analysis is based exclusively on documents because the study aimed to reconstruct educational policy and institutional developments. Interviews or observations were therefore beyond the scope of the study. As a result, the subjective perspectives of teachers and trainers, VET learners (including apprentices), and decision-makers were not captured. Quantitative data were also not included because there are currently no empirical studies on the effectiveness of support courses. This should be understood not as a methodological weakness but as a research gap. The focus on Switzerland limits the scope for international generalisation, although comparative literature was consulted. Finally, the interpretative approach inevitably involves some degree of researcher interpretation. These limitations do not diminish the relevance of the findings; rather, they indicate starting points for future research, such as triangulated designs or international comparative studies.

Disclosure statement

No potential conflict of interest was reported by the author(s).

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Data availability statement

The coding frame and codebook developed for this study are openly available at the Open Science Framework (OSF) at <https://doi.org/10.17605/OSF.IO/SHK9J>. All other sources are publicly accessible legal and policy documents, evaluation reports, and scientific literature cited in the reference list.

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